

SVM-Based Detection of SAR Images in Partially Developed Speckle Noise

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Abstract—Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a statistical learning tool that was initially developed by Vapnik in 1979 and later developed to a more complex concept of structural risk minimization (SRM). SVM is playing an increasing role in applications to detection problems in various engineering problems, notably in statistical signal processing, pattern recognition, image analysis, and communication systems. In this paper, SVM was applied to the detection of SAR (synthetic aperture radar) images in the presence of partially developed speckle noise. The simulation was done for single look and multi-look speckle models to give a complete overlook and insight to the new proposed model of the SVM-based detector. The structure of the SVM was derived and applied to real SAR images and its performance in terms of the mean square error (MSE) metric was calculated. We showed that the SVM-detected SAR images have a very low MSE and are of good quality. The quality of the processed speckled images improved for the multi-look model. Furthermore, the contrast of the SVM detected images was higher than that of the original non-noisy images, indicating that the SVM approach increased the distance between the pixel reflectivity levels (the detection hypotheses) in the original images.

Keywords—Least Square-Support Vector Machine, Synthetic Aperture Radar, Partially Developed Speckle, Multi-Look Model.

I. INTRODUCTION

RECENTLY, support vector machines (SVM's) have been introduced as a new method for solving classification and function estimation problems with many successful applications. In the remote sensing field, SVM has only been applied in the *post processing* phase for generic object recognition, classification [1], and orientation [2], [3]. Our work is novel in the sense that we apply SVM in the *image acquisition* phase while considering advanced noise models such as the single look and multi-look *partially developed speckle*, which has been suggested and verified in [4]. Specifically, we apply least square-support vector machine (LS-SVM) in the detection stage to classify the received signal in order to construct the desired image with a relatively high precision.

A detailed description of the theory of operation of SAR is lengthy and beyond the scope of this document. The reader is referred to the work of Christensen and Dich [5] for an excellent treatment of SAR systems design.

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II. SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE

Traditional detection approaches generalize poorly on image detection tasks because of the high dimensionality of the feature space. SVM can generalize well on difficult image detection problems with a superior performance to traditional techniques, including neural networks.

In this section, we provide a succinct introduction to the SVM approach. The reader is referred to the initial work of Vapnik [6] and the book of Christianini [7] for more in-depth treatment of the SVM theory.

As an intuitive approach to understanding SVM, consider a given set of points which belongs to either one of two classes. A linear SVM finds the hyperplane leaving the largest possible fraction of points of the same class on the same side, while maximizing the distance of either class from the hyperplane. This hyperplane minimizes the risk of misdetecting hypotheses of the test set. In SVM, the input vectors are nonlinearly mapped to a higher dimensional feature space. A linear discriminant function is then constructed in the new higher space, resulting in a non linear discriminant in the original input space.

We now present a brief theoretical approach to SVM. The relation between the capacity of a learning machine and its performance is ruled by a set of boundaries, which is referred to as the bound on the generalization performance. Statistical pattern recognition techniques face two problems: the identification problem and the parameters estimation problem. The identification problem is the problem of determination of the degree of freedom or complexity of the model and is generally the more complex problem [8]. The estimation problem is how to get an optimal estimate of the model parameters regarding the training data set.

Let us consider a mapping $\Phi : \square^d \mapsto H$, which maps the training data from \square^d to a higher Euclidean space H , that may have an infinite dimension. In this high dimension space, the data is linearly separable, hence linear SVM formulation above can be applied for any type of data [9]. In the SVM formulations, the training data only appear in the form of dot products $x \cdot x$. These can be replaced by dot products in the Euclidean space H , i.e., $\phi(x) \cdot \phi(x)$.

The dot product in the high dimension space can also be replaced by a kernel function. By computing the dot product directly using a kernel function, one avoids the mapping $\Phi(x)$. This is desirable because H has possibly infinite dimensions and $\Phi(x)$ can be tricky or impossible to compute. Using a kernel function, a SVM that operates in infinite dimensional space can be constructed [7].

Given a training set of N data points $\{y_k, x_k\}^N$, where x_k denotes the k^{th} input pattern and y_k the k^{th} output pattern, the SVM aims at constructing a decision function

$$f(x) = \text{sign} \left[\mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x) + b \right]$$

$$= \text{sign} \left[\sum_{k=1}^N \alpha_k y_k K(x, x_k) + b \right], \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{w} is the weight vector in the reproducing kernel Hilbert space (RKHS), α_k are support values (Lagrangian multipliers), b is the bias term, and the kernel function

$$K(x, x_k) = \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x) \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_k). \quad (2)$$

For every new test data, the kernel functions for each SV (support vector) need to be recomputed.

For any kernel function suitable for SVM, there must exist at least one pair of $\{H, \Phi\}$, such that (2) is satisfied. The kernel that has these properties is said to obey the Mercer's condition, i.e., for any $g(x)$ with finite L_2 norm,

$$\int g^2(x) dx < \infty, \quad (3)$$

$$\iint K(x, y) g(x) g(y) dx dy \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

By choosing different kernel functions, the SVM can emulate some well known classifiers [10], as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
 KERNEL FUNCTIONS' CLASSIFIERS

Kernel Function	Type of Classifier
$K(x, y) = xy$	Linear
$K(x, y) = \exp\left(-\frac{\ x - y\ _2^2}{\sigma^2}\right)$	Gaussian radial bias function (RBF)
$K(x, y) = (xy + \tau)^d$	Polynomial of degree d
$K(x, y) = \tanh(\kappa xy + \theta)$	Multi layer perceptron

While standard SVM solutions involve solving quadratic or linear programming problems, the least square version of SVM (LS-SVM), which has been adopted for this research, corresponds to solving a set of linear equations. In LS-SVM, the Mercer's condition is still applicable. Hence several types of kernels can be used, yet the RBF is the adopted one since it gives a Gaussian distribution for the errors in the feature space yielding an optimal estimate of the support values [11]. Many reasons could be stated for preferring LS-SVM over other models of SVM, yet the most important one is that LS-SVM is an iterative method that could be used to solve large scale problems with robustness in the sense of the choice of the regularization and smoothing parameters. Moreover, it offers a fast method for obtaining classifiers with good generalization performance in many real life applications.

So far, the formulation of SVM was based on a two-class problem (SVM is essentially a binary classifier). Various schemes can be applied to the basic SVM algorithm to handle

the M -class pattern classification problem. Some of these schemes [9], [12], for solving the multi-class problem are:

- Using M one-to-rest classifiers.
- Using $M(M-1)/2$ pair-wise classifiers with one of the voting schemes: Majority voting; Pairwise coupling.
- Extending the formulation of SVM to support the M class problem: By considering all classes at once; By considering each class with only the training data points belonging to that particular class.

The derivation of the multi-class LS-SVM is based on the Lagrangian optimization formulation

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}, b, \xi} \mathfrak{J}_{LS}(\mathbf{w}, \xi) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{w} + \gamma \sum_{k=1}^N \xi_k, \quad (5)$$

subject to the equality constraint

$$y_k \left[\mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_k) + b \right] = 1 - \xi_k, \quad \xi_k \geq 0, \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (6)$$

where γ is the regularization factor and ξ_k is the difference between the output y_k and discriminant function $f(x_k)$. Using standard techniques, the Lagrangian for (5) and (6) is

$$L(\mathbf{w}, b, \xi; \alpha) = \mathfrak{J}_{LS}(\mathbf{w}, \xi) - \sum_{k=1}^N \alpha_k \left[y_k \left(\mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_k) + b \right) - 1 + \xi_k \right], \quad (7)$$

where α_k are the Lagrangian multipliers corresponding to (6). The saddle point is obtained from

$$\max_{\alpha} \min_{\mathbf{w}, b, \xi} L(\mathbf{w}, b, \xi; \alpha). \quad (8)$$

This yields the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker optimality conditions:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \mathbf{w}} = 0 \rightarrow \mathbf{w} = \sum_{k=1}^N \alpha_k y_k \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_k) \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial b} = 0 \rightarrow \sum_{k=1}^N \alpha_k y_k = 0 \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \xi_k} = 0 \rightarrow \alpha_k = 2\gamma \xi_k \\ \frac{\partial L}{\partial \alpha_k} = 0 \rightarrow y_k \left[\mathbf{w}^T \boldsymbol{\varphi}(x_k) + b \right] = 1 - \xi_k \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

III. PARTIALLY DEVELOPED SPECKLE NOISE MODEL

In the single-look model, a radar resolution cell is assumed to contain a collection of N elemental point scatterers randomly distributed throughout the resolution cell, with each elementary scatterer's position distributed independently of the positions of other scatterers. The random spatial distribution of the scatterers is described by a point process with a set of points having associated complex marks E_k , ($k = 1, \dots, N$), corresponding to the backscattered electric field from the k -th scatterer. Each backscattered electric field

component E_k has a constant amplitude A_k equal to the size or reflectance strength of the k -th scatterer and a random phase φ_k , uniformly distributed over the interval $[0, 2\pi)$:

$E_k = A_k e^{j\varphi_k}$. We assume that the number of scattering points within a resolution cell is Poisson distributed with parameter Γ .

Fig. 1 LS-SVM detected speckled SAR images for different number of looks L

When electromagnetic waves are scattered from such a surface, the resultant scattered field is the superposition of the electric fields scattered by each of the elemental scatterers. The resulting process is a marked Poisson point process and $\lambda = \Gamma A$ is the intensity (or rate) of this process over a resolution cell with area A . When $\lambda(\cdot)$ is a random process, the point process is referred to as doubly stochastic marked Poisson point process [13].

SAR systems record intensity measurements of the mapped surface according to:

$$S_N = \left| \sum_{k=1}^N A_k e^{j\phi_k} \right|^2 \quad (10)$$

Speckle under this model is referred to as partially developed.

In the multilook model, L -independent diversity measurements are taken over the resolution cell by the radar. This technique involves the noncoherent sum of L statistically independent single realizations of the intensity measurements S_{Nl} ($l = 1, 2, \dots, L$) in (10) at each resolution cell:

$$T_{NL} = \sum_{l=1}^L S_{Nl} \quad (11)$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The simulations are done for single look and multi-look partially developed speckle for different images to give a complete insight to the new proposed model of the SVM-based detection. For simulation purposes, Matlab is used because of its enhanced mathematical capabilities and engineering based structure. We adopt the LS-SVM model using Matlab code downloaded from [14]. Without loss of generality and for simulation purposes, we assumed in (10) and (11) unit amplitude scatterers ($A_k = 1$) and unit parameter for the Poisson process ($\Gamma = 1$).

The resulting images from the simulation are presented in Fig. 1. We observe that the SVM-reconstructed SAR images are of very good quality for $L = 8$ looks. The quality of the reconstructed speckled images improved as the number of looks increased. The performance metric used to determine the quality of the detected images is the mean square error (MSE). The MSE results are listed in Table I.

TABLE II

THE SVM PERFORMANCE IN TERMS OF THE NUMBER OF LOOKS

No. of Looks (L)	MSE
1	3.58
2	2.16
4	1.08
8	0.43

Despite the fact that SVM is essentially a binary classifier, the approaches mentioned in section II to extend the SVM to multi-class detection worked well, as is evident from the results of the detected images, which are clearly not binary images.

Furthermore, the contrast of the SVM detected images was

higher than that of the original non-noisy images, indicating that the SVM approach increased the distance between the pixel reflectivity levels (the detection hypotheses) in the original images.

The reconstructed SAR images are observed to contain some minor spiky noise, commonly described in image processing as "salt & pepper" noise. This is due to simulation artifacts, which are inevitable in sample training based algorithms. The detected images are then post-processed using a 3x3 median filter to reduce the spiky noise effect. As shown in Fig. 1, the median filter only produced relatively good results for large number of looks. The study of post-detection filters is not the scope of this research and will be left as an area of future investigation.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we applied LS-SVM to the detection of SAR images corrupted with partially developed speckle noise using single look and multi-look models. SVM proved to be a learning machine suitable for detection problems of non binary speckled images and produced very good results for 8 look-SAR images.

SVM-based detector did also give a superior performance over the classical maximum-likelihood (ML) detectors in the digital imaging field using the SAR application.

The data used in the SVM approach is based on the underlying noise model. Consequently, snip-offs can be made to other coherent imaging systems used in remote sensing and medical imaging research with similar noise characteristics.

The results of SVM also showed an enhanced contrast. As perspective to this work, this phenomenon could be mapped to the performance of wireless communication systems, where SVM detection will increase the distance between the signals in the sense that it will make signals representing different levels almost perpendicular. This will lead, in theory, to higher signal-to-noise ratio (which is what multi-look SAR processing effectively does). This issue will be subjected to more analysis and study in order to fully understand the underlying phenomena behind such behaviour.

As future work, we also propose to examine post-detected image processing filters which are more suited to the speckle noise statistical characteristics than median filters.

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